

EU-DREAM

Effective Uptake of Digital Services to Repower European Consumers and Communities as Active Participants in Energy Transition and Markets

D2.2 DT Infrastructure

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ACRONYMS

ACRONYMS	
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CB	Communication Backbone
CS	Caching Storage
DH	Data Handler
DT	Digital Twin
DTO	Digital Twin Orchestrator
PS	Pipeline Scheduler
Protobuf	Google Protocol Buffers

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the work conducted within Task 2.2, titled “**Digital Twin Core Infrastructure**”, which spans from M1 (July 2024) to M15 (September 2025), with submission scheduled at M15.

This deliverable presents the architecture of the EU-DREAM platform, designed to coordinate simulation and AI modules within a digital twin framework. Drawing from prior work such as REPLICA, EU-DREAM evolves toward a centralised orchestration model that addresses the limitations of distributed approaches, enabling robust management of complex workflows and interactions among multiple agents. The platform introduces key innovations: a stateless orchestration service that improves scalability and resilience; a unified data model to standardise communication across components; and the combined use of Kafka for events and a Cache for transient state management. These choices ensure lightweight agent integration, efficient data exchange, and the possibility of incorporating trust-enabling mechanisms such as the DLT interface for data integrity and provenance validation.

This document details these architectural enhancements and customisations, offering a comprehensive understanding of the platform’s operational capabilities and its objectives in the field of energy management.

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Introduction

This document presents an overview of the EU-DREAM architecture, focusing on the integration of Blockchain, Digital Twin, and AI-driven components, in line with the objectives of Task 2.2. The task is in line with the general objective of the project to develop a consumer-centric, secure, and transparent energy platform capable of managing complex interactions across distributed energy resources and user-oriented services.

The primary goal of Task 2.2 is to implement the orchestration and management layer that ensures interoperability between simulation-based modules, AI agents, and data governance mechanisms. These components enable advanced energy services such as forecasting, community trading, and optimization of energy usage. The scope of the task is to develop the logical framework that coordinates their execution, ensures secure data flows, and facilitates scalability across multiple locations.

The orchestration layer developed under Task 2.2 is conceived as a multi-agent system, where autonomous components interact to achieve goals that exceed the capability of individual modules. The strength of this paradigm lies in the coordination among agents, enabling modularity, scalability, and resilience. It also provides a flexible framework for distributed decision-making, ensuring the system can adapt to evolving requirements. Within EU-DREAM, this approach is essential to ensure interoperability and transparent orchestration of modules.

To address these challenges, EU-DREAM proposes to build upon REPLICA (Rossini, 2020), a digital twin-enabling architecture developed by LINKS within the H2020 RECLAIM project¹. REPLICA was designed to interconnect heterogeneous modules, spanning both simulation-based and AI-based domains, to implement cooperative workflows. However, considering the scale and complexity of anticipated orchestration scenarios in EU-DREAM, enhancements to REPLICA are required. These include extending its capacity to manage different deployments across Living Labs, ensuring GDPR-compliant data anchoring through Blockchain, and supporting dynamic coordination of multiple agents in real-time.

The document begins with a review of the current state of distributed architectures and workflow management tools. It then outlines the principles of REPLICA, highlighting its ability to manage diversified prediction and simulation pipelines. Building on this foundation, another section explores the adaptations and extensions required to align the framework with the specific use cases of the project. Here, a detailed overview of the architecture is provided, including the data model, working principles, and components. Finally, the deliverable concludes by illustrating a potential workflow managed by the Orchestration Layer developed in this task through an example of pipeline execution.

Project Overview

The EU-DREAM project aims to make the energy system more secure, transparent, and consumer-friendly by combining blockchain technology, DTs, and AI through the use of natural language. Its ambition is to help people and communities use energy more efficiently.

¹ <https://www.reclaim-project.eu>

The project works on several fronts: establishing a secure foundation for data integrity and trust through blockchain, developing DT technology to enable real-time simulations and optimisations, and using AI to forecast consumption, optimise usage, and provide tailored recommendations. At the same time, it supports consumer participation in local energy markets by enabling communities to trade surplus energy, shift demand, and engage with energy services in a transparent and equitable way. Finally, EU-DREAM validates its solutions in real-world Living Labs across Europe, demonstrating practical benefits, scalability. Through these efforts, the project seeks to empower consumers, strengthen energy resilience, and accelerate the transition towards a decentralised and sustainable European energy system.

Task Interconnections

Task 2.2 plays a central role in the EU-DREAM architecture by linking together several elements across different work packages, as shown in Figure 1. It builds directly on the outputs of Task 1.2, which details characteristics and requirements for the architecture.

Figure 1: Relation between tasks of WP2, WP3 and WP4

Task 2.1 provides the Digital Twin models that are executed and coordinated by the infrastructure developed in Task 2.2. Their operation depends on the secured data flows managed by WP3, which defines the common data model and provides the distributed ledger-based trust mechanisms ensuring integrity and traceability. By combining these elements, Task 2.2 ensures that simulation and optimisation tasks can be carried out with reliability and accountability across distributed Living Labs.

The core infrastructure developed in Task 2.2 is then used downstream by Task 2.3 and Task 2.4, enabling integration of the NLP-based intermediary and the AI-based assistant tool. Finally, it enables the development of consumer-oriented energy services in WP4, providing the technical foundation for modules and tools that interact with end users.

State of the Art

This section presents the state of the art relevant to Task 2.2, focusing on DT architectures and orchestration mechanisms that provide the foundations for EU-DREAM's core infrastructure.

Firstly, the concept of the Digital Twin is explored, tracing its evolution and applications to energy systems. The second section addresses orchestration mechanisms, examining methods for coordinating multiple agents, ensuring scalability, and enabling communication across heterogeneous modules. The third reviews existing tools, comparing frameworks and middleware platforms that support DT deployment and agent-based orchestration, and assessing their strengths and limitations in relation to EU-DREAM's requirements. Finally, the chapter concludes with a summary and critical discussion, distilling the main insights from the review and clarifying how EU-DREAM builds upon and extends the state of the art.

Digital Twin

Digital Twin technologies have demonstrated significant potential for simulating complex processes and optimising the use of resources. Their adoption has been particularly notable in domains such as manufacturing (Alberti, 2024), energy systems (Yu, 2022), and sensor-intensive environments like Smart Cities (H. Atlam and G. Wills, 2020), where they enable the integration and harmonisation of heterogeneous data sources into a unified and dynamic representation of reality. When enriched with AI and machine learning, DTs become powerful tools for real-time monitoring, predictive analysis, and decision support.

In recent years, the DT paradigm has been applied across a wide variety of scenarios, leading to the identification of recurring technical and organisational requirements. Among the most relevant are the need for centralised or decentralised orchestration models (Rossini, 2020), depending on the scale and complexity of the system; secure access control (Harper, 2019) and restricted operations to protect sensitive information; robust data management through interoperability layers (S. Sun, 2020); and systematic quality assurance mechanisms (Ma, 2023) to ensure the reliability of simulations and insights.

Orchestration Mechanism

In modern distributed systems, the coordination of multiple agents is typically formalised as a workflow, where interdependent steps contribute to a shared goal. Two widely adopted paradigms are event choreography and orchestration. Event choreography, also used in REPLICA, as discussed in (Corradini, 2020) and (Hahn, 2018), allows components to act independently, publishing and reacting to events without a central controller. This decentralised model can offer low execution times and easy integration with other technologies, but it becomes harder to manage as workflows grow in complexity.

By contrast, orchestration introduces a central orchestrator that maintains a global view of the system, explicitly governs the execution order, and ensures traceability and control. This

centralised approach, adopted in a wide variety of use cases (Costa, 2022), (Garcia Lopez, 2018), (Svorobej, 2020), provides superior manageability but can increase overhead. Comparative studies such as (Rudrabhatla, 2018), followed by (Aydin, 2022) and (Singhal, 2019), highlight the trade-off: choreography offers performance benefits, whereas orchestration delivers clarity and robustness in complex workflows.

Existing Tools

This chapter presents a curated selection of commercial and open-source tools as a basic framework and strategic reference to guide our progress.

At the end, Table 1 will conclude this section, outlining the pros and cons of each tool.

Apache Airflow²

Apache Airflow is an open-source platform for programmatically defining, scheduling, and monitoring workflows. Initially developed by Airbnb and later contributed to the Apache Software Foundation, it is particularly suited for managing complex data pipelines. By expressing workflows as code, Airflow supports clarity, versioning, and collaborative development.

Luigi³

Luigi is a Python-based workflow management system developed by Spotify. It enables the construction of complex batch pipelines, handling task dependencies and parallel execution. Luigi prioritises simplicity and ease of use while offering a robust framework for data pipeline orchestration.

Apache Oozie⁴

Oozie is a workflow scheduler designed for the Apache Hadoop ecosystem. It supports the definition and coordination of workflows that manage the execution of Hadoop jobs and related tasks across large-scale data environments.

DigDag⁵

Digdag is a lightweight, open-source workflow engine written in Java. It is designed for ease of use, providing task scheduling and dependency management in a simple yet flexible framework.

Prefect⁶

Prefect is a modern Python-based workflow management system for orchestrating data pipelines. It allows workflows to be defined, scheduled, and monitored in code, supporting transparency and scalability.

² <https://airflow.apache.org>

³ <https://luigi.readthedocs.io>

⁴ <https://oozie.apache.org>

⁵ <https://digdag.io>

⁶ <https://prefect.io>

AWS Step Functions⁷

AWS Step Functions is a commercial cloud service for workflow orchestration provided by Amazon Web Services. It requires a paid subscription and offers serverless execution, scalability, and integration with other AWS services.

Netflix Conductor⁸

Netflix Conductor is an open source microservices orchestration engine originally developed by Netflix. While still available, it is no longer actively maintained, which limits its suitability for long-term adoption.

Comparison

Table 1: Orchestration Tools Comparison

Tool	Pros	Cons	C/OS ⁹
Apache Airflow	Mature and reliable Code-defined workflows Rich ecosystem integrations Strong monitoring tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Complex setup ○ Batch-oriented focus ○ Hard at scale ○ Steep learning curve 	OS
Luigi	Lightweight framework Python-native Strong dependency management Simple pipelines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Limited UI ● Smaller community ● No built-in scheduler ● Scaling challenges 	OS
Apache Oozie	Hadoop integration Supports diverse jobs Workflow coordination Retry mechanisms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Outdated framework ○ XML-based workflows ○ Steep learning curve ○ Hadoop-only 	OS
Digdag	Lightweight engine Portable Java-based Easy syntax Task scheduling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Small community ● Few advanced features ● Limited scalability ● Basic monitoring 	OS
Prefect	Modern design Python-native Cloud-ready Good observability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Paid advanced features ○ Less mature ○ Vendor lock-in risk ○ Limited large-scale proof 	C
AWS Step Function	Fully managed Scalable AWS integration Reliable service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Paid service ● Vendor lock-in ● Limited portability ● Verbose definitions 	C
Netflix Conductor	Microservices focus Distributed workflows Highly scalable REST APIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Not maintained ○ Complex deployment ○ Small community ○ Limited ecosystem 	OS

⁷ <https://docs.aws.amazon.com/step-functions/>

⁸ <https://github.com/Netflix/conductor>

⁹ Commercial/Open Source

Conclusion

Although REPLICIA requires adaptation to fit the pipelines of EU-DREAM, which are more complex due to the higher number of required modules, the specific needs of the project and the corresponding development of new components will be detailed in the following sections. Existing tools provide useful references for the objectives that an orchestrator component should fulfil. A key aspect to be analysed is the choice of programming language: while REPLICIA is implemented in Java, Python has been selected as the main language for the orchestration service in EU-DREAM. As shown in Table 1, many tools are either designed in or rely on Python.

Regardless of the features offered by these frameworks, the essential functionalities that the components developed in this task must implement will be later outlined.

REPLICA Architecture

REclaim oPtimization and simuLation Cooperation in digitAl twin (REPLICA) is a flexible and scalable architecture for advanced DT realisation, originally conceived and developed within the EU-funded project RECLAIM.

REPLICA enables plug-and-play deployment of models on demand and offers workflow design capabilities to orchestrate the models integrated in the DT. A principal strength lies in its ability to coordinate both simulation tasks and AI-based operations. The added value of a DT is that analyses are performed on its digital counterpart rather than on the physical asset itself. Accordingly, a DT architecture must incorporate simulation components for replicating real assets as well as prediction components to support forecasting activities. In REPLICA, the DT pipeline can be implemented in two distinct ways. In the first approach, the pipeline begins with the execution of simulation tasks, which generate the necessary input data before triggering subsequent AI models for forecasting or optimisation. In the second approach, the process starts directly with AI models, which can then call on simulations when required. This dual design increases the flexibility of the architecture, making it suitable for a wide range of application scenarios. Certain contexts demand that simulations drive the forecasting process, while in others it is more appropriate for AI components to initiate the workflow.

In this section, the discussion will concentrate on the first use case, where simulation serves as the entry point. Nevertheless, the same reasoning and design considerations can also be applied to the second approach.

However, while several features made REPLICA a Key Exploitable Result (KER) of RECLAIM, certain architectural aspects can be further improved to effectively address even the most demanding EU-DREAM scenarios. These open issues and possible enhancements will be introduced and analysed in the following section.

Overview

The architecture of REPLICA, illustrated in Figure 2, is organised into two main branches: the Simulation Environment and the AI Environment. These two execution contexts are designed to operate in combination, thereby supporting and enabling the DT paradigm. The communications between these two environments are ensured by the Communication Backbone. As REPLICA is conceived as a distributed architecture, this interface plays a central role in the overall pipeline. Information exchange must be handled efficiently to allow each module to respond to requests with minimal latency. In a DT context, multiple actors contribute to the overall outcome, making reliable and timely communication a critical requirement for the successful execution of their tasks.

Depending on its underlying logic, the backbone may also be characterised as an orchestrator. In modern microservice architectures, an orchestrator often acts as a central node that manages, organises, and redistributes messages originating from the other modules. While such a hub can foster cooperation between components, it may also introduce the risk of becoming a bottleneck. For this reason, its design is particularly critical: if implemented incorrectly, it could trigger cascading delays across all modules that depend on it.

The Simulation Environment, the AI Environment, and the Communication Backbone can be identified as the core components of REPLICA. In addition to these, other modules contribute to the overall outcome even if they are not always directly involved in the processing pipeline. Among these, the REPLICA GUI and the REST Connector are of particular importance. The former provides a backend controller that is exposed to the user through a dedicated frontend dashboard, while the latter serves as a supporting service that enables the core modules to retrieve data from external sources.

Figure 2: REPLICA logical architecture

The remainder of this section is structured as follows. The CB will be presented in the homonymous section, given its dual role as both a communication interface and an orchestration mechanism. The Simulation Environment, AI Environment, REST Connector, and REPLICA GUI will then be described in their homonymous section too.

Orchestration

The orchestration mechanism integrated into REPLICA is built upon a shared communication infrastructure. All modules within the platform can both publish and consume messages transmitted through this bus. Without adequate supervision of publishing and subscribing activities, such an approach could result in disorder and ambiguity. To mitigate this risk, the internal architectures of the Simulation Environment, AI Environment, REST Connector, and REPLICA GUI incorporate dedicated communication gateways. These gateways ensure that each component processes only the messages explicitly addressed to it, ignoring all others.

As both the backbone and the logic governing the evolution of each component represent key pillars of the orchestration mechanism, the following sections will provide a detailed analysis of these two aspects.

Communication Backbone

In REPLICA, the communication backbone is implemented using Apache Kafka, an open-source event-streaming platform particularly well suited for this context. Its architecture, with brokers, topics, partitions, and consumer groups, makes it highly effective for scenarios requiring reliable and scalable message handling.

Within this framework, each unit of data is treated as a message, stored in a partition linked to a specific topic. Owing to its ability to manage high-frequency data streams, each message is processed as an event, ensuring the responsiveness and consistency required in DT environments.

REPLICA employs three topics to exchange messages among the different branches of the architecture: the *simulation* topic, the *AI* topic, and the *REST* topic. The simulation topic contains the messages managed by the Simulation Environment, while the AI topic handles data exchanged with the AI Environment. Similarly, the REST Connector interacts exclusively with the REST topic. As a super partes component, the REPLICA GUI has the capability to access and retrieve content from both the simulation and AI topics.

This association between components and topics is not always strictly maintained. As described in the Simulation Environment subsection, it is possible for a simulator to pause an ongoing execution if it requires input generated by the AI branch. In such cases, the Simulation Environment may also read messages in the AI topic to intercept the results produced by the corresponding AI Environment.

Ultimately, this mechanism can be interpreted as a form of partial orchestration, since all modules operate with an awareness of the logic to be followed when specific conditions arise.

State Machine Model

Figure 3: Sequences of states of a simulation inside REPLICA

Inside REPLICA each operation is triggered only by events, in a completely asynchronous setting. Figure 3 shows the sequence of states that characterize the implementation of the first scenario previously described.

The execution of the DT pipeline in REPLICA begins in the REPLICA GUI. From the dashboard, the user issues a `Simulation PLANNED` message, which is published on the simulation topic and therefore can only be read by the Simulation Environment. Once the simulation is initiated, the module responds with a `Simulation RUNNING` message to inform the GUI about the progress of the pipeline.

At this stage, two execution paths are possible, depending on whether the Simulation Environment requires additional input from the AI branch. If such data is needed, the Simulation Environment first publishes a `Simulation PAUSED` message in the simulation topic, followed by an `AI PLANNED` message in the AI topic, thereby notifying the relevant AI model. The simulation remains paused until the requested result is published by the AI Environment in the AI topic. This execution flow is common in REPLICA and illustrates why the Simulation Environment must be able to both publish and read messages in both the simulation and AI topics.

During execution, once a `Simulation PLANNED` is emitted by the GUI, the selected Simulation Environment is locked until the process either completes successfully or fails, regardless of whether it requires AI support. On the AI side, it may happen that the request from the Simulation Environment is incomplete due to missing data. In such cases, the AI Environment issues a REST Request to the REST Connector by publishing the corresponding message in the REST topic. The AI process then remains blocked until the REST Connector provides the required input.

Once the REST Connector returns the needed information by publishing a REST Response in the REST topic, the AI Environment resumes execution, completes the task, and publishes an `AI COMPLETED` message. Subsequently, the Simulation Environment receives the result, completes its own workflow, and finalises the process by issuing a `Simulation COMPLETED` message.

From a logical perspective, such a pipeline is not particularly complex, as each module in the workflow is required to operate only once. The mechanism is based on a bounded form of distributed orchestration, in which each component manages its actions by considering only the messages it receives and emits during its lifecycle. Nevertheless, in more demanding scenarios, this distributed orchestration may introduce higher latency and reduce the overall efficiency of the platform.

Simulation Environment

Figure 4: Internal component of simulation environment

The Simulation Environment is responsible for managing all simulation requests executed within REPLICA. This module is composed of several key subcomponents: the Simulation Manager, the Simulation Configurator, the Result Calculator, and the simulator itself. A graphical representation of the Simulation Environment is provided in Figure 4.

All messages transmitted over the backbone are firstly received and decoded by the Communication Gateway, which acts as the input/output interface of the Simulation Environment. Once decoded, the message is passed to the Simulation Manager, which functions as the local orchestrator of the environment by coordinating the internal flow among the subsequent components.

The Simulation Configurator interprets the request and prepares the Simulator for execution. It ensures that each simulation is initiated with the specifications contained in the original request. This intermediary role enables multiple modules to cooperate towards the same goal. The configurator is also able to temporarily pause the pipeline if non-essential but beneficial data are missing, for instance, when results from other modules could improve the outcome. In REPLICA, the Simulation Configurator can be customised to check the availability of such data and, if appropriate, request additional inputs via the manager. This behaviour is particularly suited to DT pipelines, which may rely on predictions from AI models to enhance simulations.

Once the simulation is complete, the results produced by the Simulator are processed by the Result Calculator. This component transforms raw outputs into a format that can be interpreted by other modules or directly presented to the end user. The processed result is then sent back to the Communication Gateway through the Simulation Manager, closing the loop.

This internal workflow demonstrates why the Simulation Manager serves as the internal orchestrator of the Simulation Environment: every step following the reception of a backbone message is coordinated and tracked by it. The resulting sequence: backbone → gateway → manager → configurator → simulator → calculator → manager → gateway, ensures modular decoupling, as each component performs only the tasks for which it has been designed.

In Figure 4, the Configurator and the Calculator are shown within the dashed box representing the Simulation Environment. Conceptually, they belong to this environment, as they are invoked by the Simulation Manager to perform simulation tasks. From a technical perspective, however, they are implemented as isolated servers that interact with the manager through the gRPC protocol. In principle, these modules can operate entirely outside the scope of REPLICA, if they implement the required interfaces to communicate with the manager.

This design choice reflects one of the main features of REPLICA: interoperability. REPLICA is essentially a collection of software APIs that can be developed, extended, and adapted by any party wishing to employ the architecture. As a result, all modules can be regarded as independent components, while at the same time being unified through the coordination of the Communication Gateway.

AI Environment

Figure 5: Internal components of AI Environment

The AI Environment is responsible for managing all AI requests executed within REPLICA. Like the Simulation Environment, it is composed of several key components, as illustrated in Figure 5: the Communication Gateway, the AI Manager, the AI Executor, and the AI Models.

Some components of the AI Environment share features with their counterparts in the Simulation Environment, although their implementation differs according to specific requirements. In this context, the Communication Gateway is responsible for encoding and decoding messages received from the Backbone and making them available to the AI Manager.

The AI Manager oversees the execution of requests by dispatching them to the multiple AI Executors that compose the environment. The role of the AI Executor partly resembles that of the Simulation Configurator and partly that of the Result Calculator. More specifically, it converts the input received from the manager into the format required by the AI Model. The communication format is determined by the AI Model itself, which specifies its constraints to the attached executor.

Each executor can query the AI Model through two available endpoints, which differ in the external protocol they expose. In the current version of REPLICA, the AI Model can be contacted via both REST and gRPC.

REST Connector

Figure 6: Internal component of REST connector

The REST Connector is the module that enables other components to communicate with external services, either to retrieve or to publish data. As illustrated in Figure 6 the connector is composed of three main elements: the Communication Gateway, the Connector Manager, and the REST Client.

The Communication Gateway handles data exchange with the backbone by performing deserialization and serialization operations. Once a message is processed into a format that can be interpreted by the upper-layer modules, it is forwarded to the Connector Manager.

Given the overall simplicity of the REST Connector, the Connector Manager in this case has fewer responsibilities compared to other modules. Its primary function is to initiate communication with the external REST server to either pull or push data.

As described in the subsection State Machine Model and illustrated in Figure 3, the most frequent scenario occurs when REPLICA modules require external data to complete their executions. Nonetheless, pushing data is also supported, typically when workflow results produced within REPLICA must be transmitted to external systems.

The REST Client is the submodule responsible for final delivery, establishing the direct connection between REPLICA and an external server.

The rationale behind the connector design is to ensure that the architecture is not isolated from the outside world but is instead capable of effective communication with both lower-level and higher-level frameworks, potentially using a variety of protocols. In this section, the focus has been placed on REST, as in the first version of REPLICA data exchange relies on this protocol. However, the same considerations can be extended to other widely adopted communication standards.

Replica GUI

The REPLICA GUI fulfils two primary functions. First, it provides external visibility of the architecture status, including the variety of messages currently present in the topics. Second, it enables end users to initiate new REPLICA pipelines by publishing `Simulation PLANNED` and `AI PLANNED` messages in the respective simulation and AI topics.

As illustrated in Figure 7, the GUI component is technically divided into two parts, reflecting the different functional flows described above. To fulfil these roles, it is composed of the following main blocks: the Communication Gateway, the REPLICA Publisher, the REPLICA Subscriber, Format Checking, Local State, Backend REST APIs, and the Frontend.

Figure 7: Internal component of REPLICA GUI

The Communication Gateway in the GUI performs the same fundamental functions as in other REPLICA modules. It reads incoming messages from the CB and makes them available to the REPLICA Subscriber, while also serialising the messages produced by the REPLICA Publisher before sending them back into the backbone. Although this process is common across gateways, in this case, the inputs and outputs are directed to different modules. By contrast, in the Simulation Environment, both inbound and outbound data are managed centrally by the Simulation Manager. This technical choice reflects the separation of responsibilities between the GUI modules that consume and produce data.

The Format Check and the Local State serve distinct purposes. The former verifies that user-provided configurations are valid and ready for submission to the backbone. The latter functions as a local database, storing aggregated metrics and statistics derived from the data analysed by the REPLICA Subscriber. Acting as a continuous sniffer, the Subscriber monitors the topics indefinitely to compute metrics that are subsequently exposed to the user through the REST APIs.

These two modules embody the functions of the GUI most directly oriented towards user interaction. The Backend REST APIs provide access to the data stored in the Local State and expose a configuration dashboard for planning new simulations. The Frontend delivers this dashboard to the user, ensuring an accessible interface for monitoring system status and initiating new workflows.

Data Model

All messages exchanged within REPLICA are handled by the CB, which can be understood as a collection of data buckets, as described in the CB subsection. Each of these local storages is characterised by a specific data format that governs the structure of the messages it contains.

Every REPLICA module includes a Communication Gateway, serving as the bridge between the backbone and the application-specific layers built on top of it. As noted in previous sections, one of the primary functions of the gateway is to perform the serialization and deserialization of messages exchanged with the backbone. This step is crucial for two reasons: it standardises every unit of information and ensures the decoupling of logical modules from the underlying physical infrastructure.

Figure 8 illustrates the data models adopted for the messages circulating within REPLICA, along with the data model of the header. Apache Kafka enables the actors involved in communication to specify not only the content of the message but also its header. In REPLICA, this feature is exploited both to ensure that messages are delivered to the correct recipients and to include additional metadata related to the simulation pipeline.

Figure 8: Set of REPLICA data model

Header

The header illustrated in Figure 8 is particularly suited to the message that initiates the REPLICA pipeline. The source field is mainly indicative for initial messages, but becomes crucial when responding to a previous request.

For example, this occurs when the AI Environment must reply to an `AI_PLANNED` message originating from the Simulation Environment. Excluding any optional data requests to the REST Connector, the AI Environment performs a swap between the *source* and *destination* fields in the header to ensure that the response is delivered to the correct Simulation Environment.

The *destination* field is used by the communication gateways to determine whether a given message is intended for them, as well as to support the reply mechanism just described.

Although the *source* and *destination* fields are present in all messages, the *config* service and *result* service fields primarily characterise the `Simulation_PLANNED` message sent by the GUI. These fields explicitly specify the addresses of the Simulation Configurator and Result Calculator services, which are indispensable for executing the REPLICA pipeline.

Simulation Topic

The data model designed for this topic is the simplest one, as it essentially contains inputs and outputs.

The *state* field is common to both the simulation and AI topics. This variable is fundamental to the temporal evolution of a simulation request. As described in the subsection about State Machine Model, each operation within REPLICA is associated with a specific state, which functions as the metronome of the architecture. Consequently, a `Simulation_COMPLETED` message cannot exist without a corresponding `Simulation_PLANNED` message as its starting point.

The second key field is the *id*. This identifier is not merely a unique key for a single message but acts as a consistent label for the entire execution workflow. All simulation, AI, and REST events represented in the state machine of Figure 3 are logically tied to the original `Simulation_PLANNED` request, since they depend on the initial simulation task and would not exist otherwise. The *id* therefore links all events belonging to the same request, ensuring the atomicity of a REPLICA transaction involving multiple actors and datasets. This mechanism is also exploited by the GUI to present complete pipelines on the dashboard, including details on their individual progress.

Other fields play supporting roles. The *timestamp* records the exact creation time of each message. The *input_data* field stores a list of serialized files required by the simulator. The *byte_results*, *float_results*, and *string_results* fields contain the simulation output, but only when the state equals `COMPLETED`.

Generally, the data models shown in Figure 8 can be applied to both requests and responses. For simulation messages, the request is labelled with the state `PLANNED` and the response with the state `COMPLETED`. Accordingly, some variables in the model are associated with the request and others with the response, with the Simulation Manager handling the relevant data depending on the *state* field.

AI Topic

The data format that standardises the messages published in the AI topic is the most complex, as it must capture in detail the outcomes produced by the models.

The *state* field has the same function as described in the data model in the Simulation Model subsection. Likewise, its set of values is identical, indicating whether a message has been created, is in execution, paused, or completed.

The same considerations apply to the *id* field. As already explained, the *id* links together all messages that originate from the same `Simulation PLANNED` request.

The *load_data* field is a Boolean variable that indicates whether external data must be retrieved. When the Simulation Environment does not possess sufficient information to execute the requested AI model, the `AI PLANNED` message specifies the required data sources. These sources are described in a dedicated field, while the necessity is flagged through *load_data*.

Each *data_source* is defined by a *protocol* and a set of *details*. The *protocol* specifies the type of connector that must be queried, while the *details* provide the information necessary to complete the data collection. In practice, the *details* field contains the serialised protocol-dependent message to be sent to the connector. For example, when interacting with a REST server, the *details* field holds the serialised message formatted according to the model described in the REST Topic.

The *results* field is a wrapper variable that aggregates all outcomes produced by the AI task. For each result, additional details on the generating AI model can be specified, including the model type, model name, and model version. The *model_type* is restricted to a discrete set of predefined values, while the *model_name* and *model_version* are free-text strings, typically used for debugging or documentation purposes.

Each result also contains an explicit list of output values together with their associated data types. As with the model type, the type of each value is standardised and constrained to a predefined subset of allowed values. Optional complementary information on the result can also be included in the *metadata* field, providing further flexibility for monitoring, analysis, or validation.

REST Topic

This data format is entirely dependent on the protocol of the connector for which it was conceived: HTTP.

The *type* field has the same role as the *state* field used in the simulation and AI topics, but with fewer possible values. Since HTTP is a synchronous protocol, it is not necessary to represent transitory states such as paused or running. Similarly, error states are not explicitly defined, as HTTP natively encodes such conditions through specific status codes.

The *id* field differs from the identifiers used in the previous subsection. The execution of a REST task can be logically independent from the main pipeline; therefore, this identifier is decoupled from the pipeline ID adopted in the other two data models.

For requests, the *method* field specifies the REST method to be used, while the *uri* defines the resource path to be accessed. The *headers* and *body* fields further characterise the HTTP message, although both are optional (for example, GET requests may include all parameters directly in the URI).

If the message type is a *response*, the outcome of the request is represented within the result field. Since every HTTP response is defined by a *status code*, a *header*, and a *body*, these three elements are consistently included in this subfield.

Protocol Buffer

All messages stored within the three topics are serialised using Google Protocol Buffers (Protobuf). This design choice carries several important implications for the architecture.

First, the serialisation and deserialisation processes provided by Protobuf are highly efficient and optimised, reducing overall latency and improving performance.

Second, Protobuf simplifies the distribution of schemas that must be followed by all services interacting with a given topic. For instance, the Simulation Environment handles two distinct data formats: one for exchanges with the simulation topic and another for the AI topic.

Finally, Protobuf facilitates the management of data model evolution. Future enhancements to REPLICA may include the introduction of a Schema Service, capable of dynamically distributing data models to the components that rely on them. This would guarantee consistency across all exchanged messages and increase the flexibility of the architecture, making it more adaptable to rapidly evolving scenarios.

EU-DREAM Implementation

The features of REPLICA described in the previous section make it a suitable framework for EU-DREAM, as it can coordinate data flows required in simulation engines and AI models to support DT pipelines. While these elements have proven effective in earlier contexts, the requirements of EU-DREAM involve a higher level of complexity, particularly in terms of handling additional modules, ensuring efficient orchestration across multiple environments and integrating secure data flows. As a result, adaptations and extensions are needed with respect to what has already been developed and validated.

Table 2 presents the platform requirements, borrowed from those collected by T1.2 and presented in the deliverable D1.2, for defining the design specifications of the infrastructure, consistently with the pilot specifications.

Table 2: EU-DREAM Project Requirements

Requirements	
R1	Coordinate simulation agents and AI modules
R2	Allow interoperability through standardised messages structure across components
R3	Ensure scalability and flexibility via stateless and independent agents
R4	Minimise latency and resource overhead
R5	Ensure external controllability for process execution and data retrieval

Figure 9: EU-DREAM DT's infrastructure

The requirements define the essential properties of the infrastructure. To translate these requirements into a working system, the architecture shown in Figure 9 is organised around several interconnected elements that collectively ensure the orchestration of complex pipelines while preserving modularity and performance.

One group of components focuses on performance optimisation and temporal control, including the Caching Storage and the Pipeline Scheduler. The caching layer provides rapid local access to frequently used data, thereby reducing latency and avoiding repeated queries to external services. The scheduler, on the other hand, manages the timely execution of tasks and pipelines, ensuring the orderly progression of workflows even in distributed and resource-constrained environments.

The central area concerns the orchestration of processes and communication flows, addressed by the DTO and the CB. The orchestrator ensures that simulation models, AI agents and supporting services are coordinated and executed accordingly to the defined logic of the pipeline. The CB, meanwhile, provides the high-throughput, low-latency infrastructure for exchanging messages among modules using the defined data models.

Finally, the architecture integrates data handling and external interfaces, represented by the Data Handler and the Digital Twin APIs. The DH guarantees that information is properly requested, validated, and distributed across the components, while the APIs expose secure and standardised endpoints to external actors, enabling process execution and retrieval of results in a controlled manner.

The following subsections provide a detailed examination of these components. To better visualize the connections, Table 3 presents the mapping between the requirements of Table 2 and the architecture elements presented in Figure 9.

Table 3: Mapping Between Project Requirements and Architecture Components

Requirement	Component
R1	Digital Twin Orchestrator
R2	Data Model, Data Handler
R3	Communication Backbone
R4	Scheduler, Cache
R5	Digital Twin APIs

When analysing the EU-DREAM requirements, considering what REPLICa already offered, it becomes clear that several elements are inherited, while others need adaptation. REPLICa was already able to coordinate simulation and AI environments using its distributed orchestration model, but the absence of a central orchestrator made complex workflows harder to manage and less transparent. EU-DREAM addresses this by introducing a dedicated orchestration layer within the multi-agent system, which provides a global view of pipeline execution and ensures coherent coordination between simulation agents and AI modules.

Interoperability was another area where REPLICa had some limitations. Its per-topic data models serialised with Protobuf enabled efficient communication, yet the separation between simulation, AI, and REST topics created fragmentation. EU-DREAM advances this approach by defining a common data model across all components, which reduces integration overhead and allows a more consistent exchange of messages throughout the platform.

Scalability and flexibility were only partially supported in REPLICA, as managers within each environment have to maintain state, limiting the system's ability to replicate or extend components seamlessly. EU-DREAM responds to this by shifting to a stateless paradigm, where agents are independent, lightweight, and interchangeable.

On the performance side, REPLICA's use of Kafka and Protobuf already reduced communication overhead, but its distributed orchestration could still create inefficiencies in complex pipelines. EU-DREAM builds on these foundations with caching and optimised data handling services, further reducing latency and avoiding unnecessary computational load caused by repeated data access.

Finally, controllability in REPLICA was mostly limited to the GUI and the publication of specific messages, which provided only basic user interaction. EU-DREAM extends this significantly with a set of external APIs that expose secure and standardised interfaces for process execution, monitoring, and data retrieval. This evolution ensures that the platform can be more easily integrated into broader systems and controlled by external actors in a flexible and reliable way.

Overall, while REPLICA provided a strong foundation, particularly in terms of distributed communication, modularity, and efficient serialization, EU-DREAM transition toward centralised orchestration, stateless execution, harmonised data models, and extended controllability. These adaptations align the architecture with the project's requirements and make it suitable for the more demanding scenarios envisioned within EU-DREAM.

Digital Twin Orchestrator

Managing pipelines entirely in a distributed manner, as in REPLICA, is advantageous only in relatively simple scenarios where the number of modules is limited and interactions between them remain straightforward. In such cases, local orchestration within each environment is sufficient, since requests are typically addressed to a single counterpart, and the corresponding response is enough to allow the workflow to proceed. This approach is effective when dependencies between modules are minimal and can be coordinated with simple mechanisms by local managers. However, as the number of modules increases and interdependencies become more complex, the distributed orchestration model rapidly reaches its limits. The design and implementation effort grows disproportionately, and coordination becomes harder to guarantee in terms of performance, scalability, and reliability.

Centralised Management

Centralised management is introduced in EU-DREAM to overcome the limitations of the distributed orchestration approach used in REPLICA when addressing more complex scenarios. This design allows the definition and configuration of the sequences of steps required to complete a pipeline while reducing the computational burden on each component manager. In practice, components only need to react to inputs received from the orchestration service via the CB, without being concerned about the origin of the request or the downstream modules that will consume their outputs.

This orchestration mechanism also led to a redefinition of the data model, ensuring alignment with the new design principles. The common data model, exchanged through the CB, now provides a standardised structure for all interactions between the orchestrator and the other platform components, enabling interoperability and consistency across the system.

State management

Centralised orchestration introduces challenges when agents require additional data to complete their execution. If a module is forced to pause until the requested data becomes available, the entire pipeline may stall. In REPLICA, both simulation and AI environments could enter a paused state when dependent on missing information, remaining blocked until the data was retrieved from a database or another component. While duplication of modules can mitigate overload in distributed systems, this approach does not resolve the root problem of stateful dependencies, which risk causing bottlenecks and delays.

To address this, EU-DREAM promotes a stateless agent design. Each agent's output depends only on its current input, without relying on internal memory or previously stored information. For example, if an agent requests data from the DH, it does not pause while waiting. Instead, it completes its current execution and becomes immediately available for new requests. When the DH returns the required data, the orchestration layer triggers a fresh task for the same agent, allowing continuous responsiveness. This model not only avoids idle waiting but also makes horizontal scaling more effective, since replicas of stateless agents can be introduced seamlessly without concern for shared state. The same principle applies to the orchestration component. Although workflow execution is inherently stateful, the orchestrator must avoid storing pipeline state locally. If the state is tightly coupled with the orchestrator instance, any failure risks losing execution progress, while overload prevents horizontal scaling.

Statelessness

The stateless design, which is innovative in centralised orchestration architectures, has been introduced in EU-DREAM to ensure scalability and fault tolerance in orchestrated workflows. A pipeline in this context refers to a coordinated sequence of agent executions that together achieve a specific objective. By definition, a pipeline is a stateful operation, as it requires maintaining execution context across tasks to guarantee correct sequencing and consistent data flow. A straightforward way to manage this context is to adopt a stateful design. In distributed systems, this generally means that the orchestrator stores the data needed for task execution locally. In a centralised architecture, the orchestrator would then act both as the communication hub coordinating task execution and as the component responsible for storing pipeline state. While this simplifies orchestration and allows fast local decisions, it also creates strong coupling between logic and state. This coupling hampers scalability, complicates replication, and risks desynchronisation or loss of execution context in the event of a failure. As a result, the orchestrator itself can easily become a bottleneck when multiple pipelines are executed in parallel.

To avoid these issues, EU-DREAM adopts a stateless design for the DTO. In this model, the state is not stored locally but is managed in a distributed manner across the architecture. The orchestrator instances remain lightweight and replicable, so that any replica can independently process incoming requests. This makes it possible to scale orchestration horizontally and to maintain robustness against failures without sacrificing coordination or consistency.

The DT APIs provide the interface for submitting pipeline requests and monitoring their progress, while the orchestration logic ensures that the execution context is propagated in a distributed fashion rather than retained internally. In this way, EU-DREAM achieves a balance between the unavoidable statefulness of workflows and the benefits of a stateless orchestration architecture, combining resilience, scalability, and efficiency.

Workflow Preprocessing

At the core of the stateless orchestration solution in EU-DREAM lies a preprocessing module referred to as the splitter. This component bridges the gap between high-level workflow definitions and the operational requirements of stateless orchestration. To support this design, workflows submitted by users are decomposed into collections of independent subworkflows, each representing an atomic task executable in isolation. This decomposition enables replicas of the DTO to process subworkflows independently, removing reliance on local state and ensuring scalable, resilient execution. Whenever a workflow is submitted through the DT APIs, the splitter performs several key tasks: it validates the workflow against platform requirements and checks compatibility with currently deployed agents; it converts the workflow definition from a standardised JSON format into an executable Python script; it decomposes the workflow into atomic subworkflows; it adapts each subworkflow for standalone execution; and finally, it stores the subworkflow definitions for subsequent retrieval by the orchestrator.

In this execution model, each workflow is compiled into a Python script composed of functions standardised by the internal orchestration library. Functions are classified as non-blocking, when they can be completed entirely within the orchestrator, or blocking, when they require external interaction with other components such as the DH, external applications, or the user. Blocking functions define the logical boundaries of subworkflows: each subworkflow concludes by publishing a message on the CB, while the corresponding response triggers the execution of the next subworkflow.

This event-driven decomposition produces loosely coupled, stateless subworkflows that can be executed independently and in parallel if required. Each subworkflow is implemented as a standalone Python script containing a run function, which accepts two inputs: an object carrying execution metadata, and a dictionary containing the accumulated variables from previous subtasks. This structure ensures that the execution context is explicitly passed between subtasks without relying on local memory, thereby achieving stateless orchestration.

Although the DTO is designed to operate without storing execution state locally, workflow execution still requires passing context between tasks. At the end of each subworkflow, and before publishing the message that marks its completion, the orchestrator collects the variables generated during the execution. These variables represent the state accumulated up to that point and form the necessary context for the subsequent task. To achieve this, the orchestrator inspects the execution environment, extracts the relevant local variables, and filters out auxiliary data so that only meaningful context is retained. The resulting information is then encoded to ensure compatibility with the message format and included in the payload. Alongside the execution context, the message also carries the identifier of the subworkflow (e.g., subworkflow-1, subworkflow-2), which ensures that the correct subsequent task is triggered upon reception.

This mechanism allows context to be explicitly passed from one subworkflow to the next, rather than being maintained internally by the orchestrator. In doing so, EU-DREAM preserves the stateless design principle while guaranteeing that the orchestration logic remains consistent, reliable, and scalable.

Platform Operator

The deployment and lifecycle management of agents are handled internally by the Platform Operator function (Figure 10). This mechanism follows the Kubernetes Operator pattern¹⁰, which extends cluster capabilities by defining custom resources with dedicated roles, permissions, and behaviours.

Figure 10: Platform Operator capabilities

The operator automates the creation and configuration of agents by generating the corresponding pods, injecting configuration variables, and monitoring their lifecycle. Each agent is described by a manifest that specifies its parameters, while a Platform manifest defines the shared system services (databases, brokers, caches, etc.) and authentication credentials. By linking agent manifests to the platform manifest through metadata labels, the orchestrator ensures that agents are consistently configured and bound to the correct platform instance. This integration allows the orchestrator not only to coordinate workflows at runtime, but also to manage the infrastructure supporting them. The operator interacts with Kubernetes APIs to provision certificates and ensure that deployed agents remain aligned with platform policies. In this way, the DTO becomes responsible for both execution logic and operational management, consolidating control within a single architectural component.

¹⁰ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/extend-kubernetes/operator>.

Communication Backbone

The communication backbone in EU-DREAM is implemented using Apache Kafka¹¹, an open-source event-streaming platform designed for high-throughput and low-latency message exchange. Kafka provides the distributed infrastructure needed to connect simulation agents, AI modules, and supporting services, ensuring reliable delivery of messages even under demanding conditions.

Messages are organised into topics, which structure the communication flows among different components of the architecture. By design, Kafka supports scalability through partitioning and replication, enabling parallel processing of messages and resilience to node failures. Its publish-subscribe mechanism also ensures that each component receives only the messages relevant to its operation, reducing unnecessary overhead. These features distinguish Kafka from traditional messaging protocols such as MQTT, positioning it not as a broker for message exchange but as a distributed event-streaming platform.

An important feature of Kafka is its ability to maintain a configurable history of messages within each topic, providing persistence, ordered delivery, and replayability. This capability is particularly relevant as it allows newly created or restarted agents to subscribe to a topic and instantly synchronise with the current state of the pipeline. By replaying past events, agents can reconstruct the execution context without requiring additional orchestration logic or direct reconfiguration. This mechanism ensures that even in dynamic environments, where agents may be deployed, replaced, or scaled on demand, each component remains fully aware of pipeline progress and task dependencies.

Caching Storage

While the DTO operates without storing execution state locally, workflow execution still requires propagating context between subworkflows. Two strategies were evaluated to address this need. The first consisted of appending all state variables directly to the messages exchanged over Kafka. Although conceptually straightforward, this approach presented clear drawbacks: it required each agent to return the full accumulated state, making the pipeline fragile in case of incomplete responses, and it caused the message size to grow linearly with the number of tasks. To overcome these limitations, EU-DREAM adopts a second strategy based on the use of a temporary, in-memory cache using Redis¹². In this design, variables generated at the end of each subworkflow are encoded and stored in the cache. Before the next subworkflow starts, the stored context is retrieved and passed forward as a dictionary of variables. At runtime, this dictionary is decoded and reconstructed into the local context, allowing execution to resume as if it were part of a continuous, stateful pipeline, while the orchestrator itself remains stateless. This solution avoids transmitting large payloads through Kafka, thereby preserving its role as an event broker rather than a data store. The cache is centralised and transient: it is accessible to all components during pipeline execution but is automatically cleared once execution completes, preventing unnecessary memory consumption. The overhead introduced by read and write operations was found to be negligible, while the benefits in scalability and efficiency are substantial.

¹¹ <https://kafka.apache.org/documentation>

¹² <https://redis.io/docs/latest/>

Data Model

The integration of communication modules with different goals and functionalities, operating across heterogeneous environments, requires the standardisation of the messages they exchange. Without a common structure, interoperability between agents, orchestrator, and data services would be limited and error prone. The data model has been designed for the specific needs of orchestration and for the interactions with the DH and other platform components.

In this section, the focus is placed on explaining the rationale for these adaptations, showing how the data model has been customised to support the orchestration design and to ensure consistency across the entire CB.

Header

```
«phase»: <INFERENCE|TRAINING>, «agent»: <agent id>, «state»: <PLANNED|PAUSED|COMPLETED|STOPPED|ERROR>, «issuer»: <user>
```

Agent Task

```
{
  «state»: <PLANNED|PAUSED|COMPLETED|STOPPED|ERROR>,
  «phase»: <INFERENCE|TRAINING>,
  «id»: <task id>,
  «agent»: <agent id>,
  «issuer»: <user group that used the Platform APIs>,
  «timestamp»: <timestamp of generation>,
  «timeout»: <maximum execution time allowed>,
  «data»: <optional configuration data>,
  «task_restart»: <following split of the workflow>,
  «variables»: <variables of the last workflow split>
}
```

Orchestrator Task

```
{
  «state»: <PLANNED|COMPLETED|STOPPED|ERROR>,
  «id»: <task id>,
  «issuer»: <user group that used the Platform APIs>,
  «timestamp»: <timestamp of generation>,
  «timeout»: <maximum time allowed for the execution>,
  «schedule_id»: <optional corresponding schedule>,
  «workflow»: <name of the workflow>,
  «data»: <optional configuration data>,
}
```

Data Task

```
{
  «state»: <REQUEST|RESPONSE>,
  «id»: <data task id>,
  «issuer»: <user group that used the Platform APIs>,
  «timestamp»: <timestamp of generation>,
  «data_source»: <agent task data souce> {...}
  «data»: <optional configuration data>,
  «task_restart»: <following split of the workflow>,
  «variables»: <variables of the last workflow split>
}
```

Scheduler Task

```
{
  «request»: <PLANNED|CANCELLED>,
  «trigger»: <TIME|DATA>,
  «state»: <ACCEPTED|REJECTED|ERROR>,
  «id»: <task id>,
  «issuer»: <user group that used the Platform APIs>,
  «timestamp»: <timestamp of generation>,
  «start_time»: <start time of the schedule>,
  «include_start»: <include start_time as trigger>,
  «repeat_pattern»: <pattern for scheduling events>,
  «topic»: <MQTT topic that triggers the event>,
  «workflow»: <workflow to execute>
}
```

Figure 11: EU-DREAM Data Model

The introduction of centralised orchestration in EU-DREAM also results in the centralisation of the data model. All interactions between the DTO and the platform components are standardised into a coherent set of data models, each accepted by the CB. Figure 11 illustrates these models, which are exchanged over Kafka topics dedicated to specific communication flows.

The orchestrator topic carries `Orchestrator Tasks`, enabling interactions between the user and the orchestrator. The agent topic supports communication between the orchestrator and individual agents, transmitting `Agent Tasks`. Finally, the data topic connects the orchestrator with the DH, exchanging `Data Tasks`. Together, these topics provide a unified structure for pipeline execution and ensure interoperability across the platform.

The design of the `Data Task` represents a clear point of departure from the REPLICA project. In REPLICA, where orchestration is distributed across modules, data retrieval requests are made directly by the components that require information to complete their execution. For example, simulation or AI modules can query the DH without the involvement of an overarching service. In EU-DREAM, two alternative strategies were considered. The first replicates the REPLICA mechanism, allowing simulation or decision-support modules to interact directly with the DH via the CB. This solution reduces the responsibilities of the orchestration service, which can focus solely on coordinating pipeline steps. However, it also requires each agent to manage separate communication channels: one for execution and results, and another for data exchange. This approach introduces additional complexity in the integration of new modules.

The second strategy aligns with the principles of centralised orchestration. Here, data requests are specified within the workflow definition and managed by the DTO. In this case, the orchestrator itself contacts the DH on behalf of the requesting component. While this approach increases the orchestrator's responsibilities, it simplifies agent design and ensures consistent handling of data access across the platform.

In both strategies, all interactions with the DH must pass through dedicated communication channels. Since the CB is implemented with Apache Kafka, this separation is achieved by defining distinct topics: one for execution and result flows, and another dedicated to data retrieval and response.

The second solution has been adopted with the goal of simplifying agent integration into the platform. By managing all critical tasks internally and routing them through the Orchestration Service, the system reduces the complexity on the agent side.

The `Scheduler Task` is responsible for handling both time-based and data-based triggers, which are distinguished in the task definition by a dedicated trigger key. Unlike other task types, the meaning of its `state` field is specific: rather than describing an execution phase, it indicates whether the requested scheduling action has been successfully accepted by the system.

The header shown in Figure 11 is essential to provide components with a concise overview of each received message. Since all payloads are encoded in Protobuf to minimise communication overhead, the header acts as a lightweight summary that avoids unnecessary decoding. In particular, the combination of the `issuer`, `agent_id`, `phase`, and `status` fields enables agents to quickly determine which messages from the agent topic should be processed and which can be ignored. For instance, the orchestrator only accepts messages from the agent topic when the `status` field is set to `COMPLETED`. Messages with a `PLANNED` status may have been produced by the same orchestrator or by another replica and are therefore filtered out. This mechanism saves time by preventing full payload processing when it is not required.

This design choice also simplifies platform management. Rather than dynamically creating a dedicated Kafka topic for each deployed agent, EU-DREAM relies on only three main topics: orchestrator, agent, and data. The use of header fields enables fast checks at the message level without increasing the number of topics. In this respect, the header fields serve the same role as in REPLICA, allowing each component to identify whether a message is relevant.

Agent Proxy

In EU-DREAM, each agent is coupled with a proxy, an infrastructure element that mediates its interaction with the CB. The proxy performs functions like those of the communication gateway in REPLICA, but extends them with additional capabilities.

On the one hand, the proxy translates the high-level commands of the orchestrator into specific actions for the agent, such as reading or writing messages on the CB. It also ensures that outgoing data is formatted correctly and that incoming data is converted into the standardised structure defined by the platform's data model. This guarantees seamless interoperability between heterogeneous agents and the orchestration environment.

On the other hand, the proxy provides visibility into the operational status of the agent. By monitoring activity and reporting back to the orchestrator, it enables the platform to track the availability, workload, and health of agents in real time. This monitoring capability strengthens fault tolerance and supports horizontal scalability, as orchestrator decisions can be based on the most up-to-date view of agent conditions.

Pipeline Scheduler

Figure 12: Pipeline Scheduler architecture

The Pipeline Scheduler, represented in Figure 12, is responsible for managing the execution of pipelines according to both time-based and data-based triggers. Time-based triggers rely on the internal clock of the DTO, enabling executions to be planned at specific intervals or defined moments. Data-based triggers, instead, are activated when the orchestrator subscribes to the topic associated with a target variable and initiates execution upon receiving the corresponding message.

The platform exposes a set of DT APIs that allow users to configure new schedules or query information about existing ones. User-defined configurations are transformed into standardised messages by the API module and then published to the CB. The PS consumes these Scheduler messages, applies the specified parameters, and manages the execution of the associated pipelines.

Data Handler

The Data Handler manages requests originating from the orchestration environment. These requests, formatted according to the Data Tasks model, are transmitted through the CB. Once received, the DH translates the request into a query for the Data Platform and reformats the result back into the Data Task model for the requesting component. To avoid transmitting large payloads via Kafka, results are temporarily stored in the Cache component, allowing components to retrieve information directly without repeatedly querying the Data Platform. The DH also interacts with the DLT interface, which validates the integrity and provenance of the retrieved information. This mechanism ensures that data used in simulations and AI tasks can either be trusted or, if validation fails, explicitly marked as not trustworthy. By combining access to heterogeneous sources with caching for efficiency and DLT verification for trust, the DH acts as the bridge between orchestration and the underlying data services, enabling consistent and dependable workflows within EU-DREAM.

Digital Twin APIs

Figure 13: Digital Twin APIs capabilities and communications

The Digital Twin API is responsible for exposing the platform’s functionalities externally. Since EU-DREAM relies on the DTO to coordinate pipeline execution, this component primarily enables the configuration and management of orchestration workflows. While orchestration configuration is its core function, the DT API also provides users with a broader view of platform activity. This includes monitoring the status of pipelines, as well as tracking the condition of agents and the progress of workflows. To support these functions, the internal blocks of the module are organised into distinct capabilities, as illustrated in Figure 13.

Each capability stores information derived from messages exchanged within the platform, so that it can be efficiently retrieved and presented to users when an API endpoint is queried. In this way, the DT API acts as both a control and monitoring interface: it enables external configuration of workflows and provides visibility into the state of the platform at runtime.

Platform Management

GET	/platform/issuer	Get Authenticated Issuer
GET	/platform/agents	Get Running Agents

Figure 14: APIs for managing the platform.

The endpoint in the Platform Management section (Figure 14) can be used to verify that all agents deployed via the manifest are active. This same endpoint also allows checking for the presence of replicas, which is particularly useful when running tests. The agents returned in the response are those associated with the issuer *living_lab*, which serves as the issuer. Figure 15 shows the endpoint to be contacted, the parameters required in the request, and the response model generated by the platform when the operation is successfully executed.

```
curl -X 'GET' \
  'https://dream.linksfoundation.com/api/platform/agents' \
  -H 'accept: application/json' \
  -H 'Authorization: Bearer {token}'

{
  "issuer": "living_lab",
  "agents": {
    "thermal-model": 1,
    "energy-forecasting": 1,
    "energy-optimisation": 1,
  }
}
```

Figure 15: Endpoint for verifying that all the agents needed are deployed.

Agent Configuration

GET	/config/{agent_type}	Get Agent Configuration
POST	/config/{agent_type}	Store Agent Configuration
DELETE	/config/{agent_type}	Delete Agent Configuration

Figure 16: APIs for configuring the Agents.

After confirming that all agents have been successfully deployed on the platform, each agent can be configured according to the required setup (Figure 16, Figure 17). For the energy-optimisation agent, the configuration parameters are included in the body of a *POST* request, as illustrated in Figure 18.

```
curl -X 'GET' \
  'https://dream.linksfoundation.com/api/config/energy-optimisation' \
  -H 'accept: application/json' \
  -H 'Authorization: Bearer {token}'

-----
{
  "pilot": "*",
  "agent_type": "energy-optimisation",
  "data": {
    "m3": 24,
    "thermal-coefficient": 0,
    ...
  },
  "last_updated": "2025-09-15T15:00:00.000000"
}
```

Figure 17: Endpoint for verifying the agent configuration

```
curl -X 'POST' \
  'https://dream.linksfoundation.com/api/config/energy-optimisation' \
  -H 'accept: application/json' \
  -H 'Authorization: Bearer {token}' \
  -H 'Content-Type: application/json' \
  -d '{
    "m3": 24,
    "thermal-coefficient": 0,
    ...
  }'
```

Figure 18: Endpoint for configuring the agents

Pipeline Management

POST	/run	Run Pipeline
GET	/pipeline/list	List Pipelines
GET	/pipeline/{pipeline_id}	Get Pipeline Information
GET	/pipeline/details/{pipeline_id}	Get Pipeline Details
GET	/pipeline/result/{pipeline_id}	Get Pipeline Result
DELETE	/pipeline/{pipeline_id}	Delete Pipeline

Figure 19: APIs for managing the pipelines.

The Pipeline capability in Figure 19 provides information on the pipelines currently in execution. Since each pipeline consists of messages that may represent either agent executions or data requests, this capability also leverages the statistics produced by the Agent and Data submodules. These submodules continuously inspect and analyse the messages exchanged between the DTO and the target modules, compiling an internal set of statistics. This information can then be presented to the user whenever required, for example, to report the progress of a pipeline or to provide the complete set of details characterising a specific execution. The following sections describe in detail the types of messages returned by the most relevant APIs exposed by this capability.

Pipeline Run

```
{
  "status": "PLANNED",
  "id": "81ad4c20-16ff-4dde-9429-27ca2187c74c"
}
```

Figure 20: Response model of the API /pipeline/run

```
curl -X 'POST' \
  'https://dream.linksfoundation.com/api/pipeline/run?workflow=energy-optimization&timeout=600' \
  -H 'accept: application/json' \
  -H 'Authorization: Bearer {token}' \
  -H 'Content-Type: application/json' \
  -d '{}'
```

Figure 21: Endpoint for executing pipeline for the workflow "energy-optimisation"

The /run API allows users to execute a specific workflow on the platform. When invoked, the DT API translates the request into an `Orchestration Task` message, which is then processed by one of the orchestrators during execution. In addition, the set of Pipeline Management APIs provides endpoints for monitoring and controlling running pipelines. These APIs not only allow the execution of new workflows but also enable users to retrieve information about ongoing processes. The `POST` and `DELETE` endpoints support the creation and termination of pipeline executions, while the response model returns a simple structure containing the status and the identifier of the scheduled pipeline, as illustrated in Figure 20 and Figure 21.

Pipeline List

The /pipeline/list endpoint (Figure 23) returns the complete list of pipelines currently managed by the platform, including their respective identifiers and execution status.

```
curl -X 'GET' \
  'https://dream.linksfoundation.com/api/pipeline/81dd3506-841d-429e-8acf-84f616c95cf0' \
  -H 'accept: application/json' \
  -H 'Authorization: Bearer {token}'
```

Figure 22: Endpoint for verifying the state of the pipeline

This provides a high-level overview of all ongoing and past workflows, supporting monitoring and debugging activities.

```
[
  {
    "id": "a3c3184a-08f8-4d21-be65-986bb15fdfb8",
    "start": "2025-09-11T16:12:43",
    "timestamp_start": 1757599963345,
    "state": "COMPLETED",
    "workflow": "simulation_1",
    "issuer": "living_lab",
    "end": "2025-09-11T16:14:11",
    "timestamp_end": 1757600051058
  },
  {
    "id": "2cf8afd4-badf-41ea-923c-aecc5df37eaf",
    "start": "2025-09-11T13:57:08",
    "timestamp_start": 1757591828756,
    "state": "COMPLETED",
    "workflow": "flow-test",
    "issuer": "suan",
    ...,
  }
]
```

Figure 23: Response model of the API `/pipeline/list`.

The `/pipeline/{pipeline_id}` endpoint (Figure 22) offers the same type of information but restricted to a single pipeline, filtered by the provided identifier. This allows users to inspect the progress and details of a specific execution without retrieving the entire list.

```
curl -X 'GET' \
  'https://dream.linksfoundation.com/api/pipeline/result/a3c3184a-08f8-4d21-be65-986bb15fdfb8?issuer=living_lab' \
  -H 'accept: application/json' \
  -H 'Authorization: Bearer {token}'
-----
{
  "status": "COMPLETED",
  "id": "a3c3184a-08f8-4d21-be65-986bb15fdfb8",
  "data": [...]
}
```

Figure 24: Endpoint to retrieving the result of a pipeline

The endpoint `/result/{pipeline_id}` shown in Figure 24 provides the same information returned by `/pipeline/{pipeline_id}`, but with the addition of a data field. This field contains the output generated by the entire pipeline execution.

```

{
  "id": "e47d46e1-6055-448e-885a-bc004999ef16",
  "start": "2025-09-11T09:22:26",
  "timestamp_start": 1757575346560,
  "state": "COMPLETED",
  "workflow": "simulation_1",
  "issuer": "living_lab",
  "end": "2025-09-11T10:22:07",
  "timestamp_end": 1757578927839,
  "details": [
    {
      "id": "13000891-9771-4caf-ada0-39935f6ccafe",
      "timestamp": 1757576026000,
      "agent": {
        "name": "Orchestrator"
      },
      "state": "PLANNED"
    },
    {
      "id": "db8f5dd5-b819-4321-bcbe-eb812993e455",
      "timestamp": 1757576176000,
      "agent": {
        "id": "agent-test",
        "name": "agent-test"
      },
      "state": "PLANNED"
    },
    {
      "id": "721d4ad9-e83d-44df-af6c-b4f8ab9d4bb2",
      "timestamp": 1757575714000,
      "agent": {
        "id": "agent-test",
        "name": "agent-test"
      },
      "state": "COMPLETED"
    },
    {
      "id": "75d85893-54b8-41ff-a8ed-2fa750a0228b",
      "timestamp": 1757575348000,
      "agent": {
        "name": "Orchestrator"
      },
      "state": "COMPLETED"
    }
  ]
}

```

Figure 25: Response model of the API /pipeline/details/{pipeline_id}

Pipeline Details

The /details/{pipeline_id} endpoint (Figure 25) enables inspection of the individual steps of a pipeline. It returns a complete list of the executed steps, including the timestamp of each request and the corresponding response.

This level of detail allows operators to trace the exact sequence of actions performed during pipeline execution and to analyse the behaviour of agents and data exchanges over time. This API is mainly intended for debugging and troubleshooting purposes, so access permissions are restricted to platform managers.

Scheduler

GET	/schedule/list	List Schedules
GET	/schedule/{schedule_id}	Get Schedule Information
POST	/schedule/time	Create Time Schedule
POST	/schedule/data	Create Data Schedule
DELETE	/schedule/{schedule_id}	Delete Schedule

Figure 26: APIs for scheduling the execution of the pipelines

Once the procedure has been verified, the pipeline can be scheduled (Figure 26) to run periodically. This is achieved by submitting a *POST* request to the endpoint illustrated in Figure 27, specifying both the desired start time and the repetition pattern (e.g., hourly or daily). In this way, recurring executions can be configured directly from the scheduling interface, ensuring that workflows are triggered automatically according to the defined plan.

```
curl -X 'POST' \
  'https://dream.linksfoundation.com/api/schedule/time?start_time=2025-08-29T12%3A00%3A00Z&repeat_pattern=hourly&workflow=energy-optimisation.py' \
  -H 'accept: application/json' \
  -H 'Authorization: Bearer {token}' \
  -d ''
```

Figure 27: Endpoint to schedule a periodic and automatic execution of the pipeline.

Schedule List

The `/schedule/list` endpoint allows users to retrieve all schedules associated with them. The platform automatically uses the authentication token to identify the user and filters the response accordingly, ensuring that only relevant schedules are displayed. The returned data model follows the structure illustrated in Figure 28.

For more detailed information about a specific schedule, the `/schedule/{schedule_id}` endpoint is available. This endpoint provides the details of the selected schedule only, using the same data format shown in Figure 28, without including other entries.

Schedule Create and Delete

For both the registration and deletion of a schedule, the response model follows the same structure illustrated in Figure 29. Within this model, the `status` field indicates the outcome of the operation: `PLANNED` corresponds to the successful registration of a new scheduling logic, while `CANCELLED` denotes the deletion of an existing one. This approach ensures that all scheduling operations return a consistent and easily interpretable response.

```
{
  "id": "99996edc-2f11-4af8-b826-61d4d71b560f ",
  "request": "PLANNED/CANCELED",
  "trigger": "TIME",
  "workflow": "load_balancing_workflow",
  "start_time": "2025-09-12T12:00:00Z",
  "repeat_pattern": "hourly"
}
```

Figure 28: Response model of the APIs POST and DELETE /schedule/{schedule_id}

```
[
  {
    "id": "40f4ae92-67df-4681-8272-11bd5c74aaa4",
    "request": "PLANNED",
    "trigger": "DATA",
    "workflow": "simulation-workflow",
    "topic": "dream/living_lab/<variable>"
  },
  {
    "id": "99996edc-2f11-4af8-b826-61d4d71b560f",
    "request": "PLANNED",
    "trigger": "TIME",
    "workflow": "energy-optimisation",
    "start_time": "2025-09-12T12:00:00Z",
    "repeat_pattern": "hourly"
  }
]
```

Figure 29: Response Model of the API /schedule/list

Workflow

POST	/workflow/upload/{issuer}	Upload Workflow
GET	/workflow/list/name	List Workflows by Name
GET	/workflow/list/version	List Workflows by Versions
GET	/workflow/{workflow_name}	Get Workflow Information
DELETE	/workflow/{workflow_name}	Delete Workflow

Figure 30: APIs for managing the workflow files.

The Workflow submodule (Figure 30) manages the collection of workflow recipes available to each user. It provides functionality for uploading new workflows and for inspecting all workflows associated with a specific issuer.

```
{
  "result_logging": [
    "Info: New workflow for issuer iren:simulation.py was
      uploaded as minio_object on the bucket",
    "Info: Subworkflow simulation are not in bucket, for
      the issuer iren, so it is the first active version for
      this workflow",
    "Info: Subworkflows were uploaded in the path
      iren/simulation "
  ],
  "result_workflow_uploaded": [
    {
      "name": " iren/simulation_1.py ",
      "version": "1c20283b-54ef-4223-b0dd-8327fa402a4c"
    },
    {
      "name": " iren/simulation/simulation_1-1.py",
      "version": "5af72b1d-5809-41e1-94d9-f2b2bcdf9d7c"
    },
    {
      "name": " iren/simulation/simulation_1-2.py",
      "version": "1e77e8b4-57bb-4349-a0ba-cb6ebc87affe"
    }
  ],
  "result_subworkflow_deleted": []
}
```

Figure 31: Response model for the API /workflow/upload/{issuer}

Workflow Creation

The creation API shown in Figure 31 returns detailed logging information for each operation, including metadata about the uploaded file in storage, the main workflow, and its associated sub-workflows. If a workflow with the same name already exists, the system removes the previous sub-workflows while retaining versioning only for the main workflow.

This choice is motivated by efficiency: sub-workflows can always be reconstructed from the main workflow, making it unnecessary to store redundant copies and thus optimising storage usage.

```
import uuid

from core.orchestration import execute_agent, finish, get_agent_result
from core.encoding import decode_variable

from mas.model.agent import Agent
from mas.model.task import TaskRequest
from mas.model.orchestrator import OrchestratorTask

async def run(request: OrchestratorTask, variables: dict= {}):

    module1 = Agent(id="agent-test", name="agent-test")

    task1 = TaskRequest(
        agent=module1,
        data={
            "hello": "world"
        }
    )

    id = str(uuid.uuid4())
    await execute_agent(id, request, task1)
    res1 = await get_agent_result(id)
```

Figure 32: Response model of the API `/workflow/list/version`

Workflow List

The `/workflow/list` endpoint in Figure 32 allows users to retrieve the list of workflows associated with their issuer, which is automatically identified from the authentication token.

Workflow Get

The list can be configured to include all workflows, both active and inactive versions, or filtered to show only active ones. For this purpose, the `/workflow/list/name` endpoint is available.

The platform maintains versioning for each individual workflow, allowing users to retrieve and, if necessary, restore earlier versions. This functionality is exposed through the `/workflow/{workflow_name}` endpoint, which returns the definition of the workflow associated with the specified name.

Orchestration Flow

The data pipelines executed by the platform involve multiple communications and exchanges between different components. This architectural choice is motivated by the need to provide a complete abstraction layer for all operational agents while also optimising the flow of information across the system. In the following subsections, the overall interaction between modules will be examined, with particular attention to the technical trade-offs associated with this design. The analysis will highlight how communication patterns and orchestration logic balance performance, scalability, and integration complexity. The execution of a pipeline begins with the deployment of all components and agents selected by the user. Each agent can be instantiated multiple times and can serve different users simultaneously, supporting both scalability and multi-user operation.

Agent Configuration and Upload

Figure 33: APIs for configuring an agent and uploading a workflow.

At runtime, users can exploit the `/configure` command to dynamically parameterise the agent APIs. The chosen settings are stored in the CS and made available to the relevant agents before execution. This mechanism allows agents to remain lightweight and stateless, as they can retrieve all required parameters directly from the infrastructure rather than maintaining them locally. Figure 33 illustrates this phase (steps 1–3), which is optional and depends on the specific use case. It also depicts the activities carried out by the DT APIs during workflow onboarding. When a new workflow is uploaded, the system first performs a syntax and consistency check (step 6). Depending on the outcome, the workflow may either be split into multiple sub-workflows (steps 7–10) or retained as a single block (step 11). When workflows are segmented, the resulting sub-workflows persisted in the CS, allowing the DTO to retrieve them at runtime and coordinate their execution.

Pipeline Run

The sequence diagram in Figure 34 illustrates the execution of a pipeline once it has been configured and admitted into the EU-DREAM platform.

Lines 1–3 represent the initial trigger, where a user (or an external system) requests the execution of a workflow through the DT APIs. This request is translated into an Orchestrator Task and published on the CB, where it is received by the DTO. From lines 4–7, the orchestrator decomposes the workflow into its corresponding tasks and dispatches them to the selected agents through their proxies. Each proxy ensures proper message formatting, status reporting, and manages the interface between the infrastructure and the agent. If the execution requires data, the orchestrator issues a Data Task towards the DH, which retrieves the required information from the underlying data platform. To avoid overloading Kafka, results are cached in the Cache component, making them directly available for subsequent steps. Lines 8–10 describe the feedback loop: once an agent completes its task, it publishes a completion message on the backbone. The orchestrator then fetches the relevant context from the Cache, updates the workflow state, and triggers the following subworkflow. This ensures that the pipeline progresses smoothly, while the orchestrator itself remains stateless and replicable. Finally, in lines 11–12, the orchestrator assembles the results and publishes the outcome of the pipeline.

The sequence diagram in Figure 35 illustrates a pipeline execution scenario in which agents require access to external data to complete their tasks.

Lines 1–3 show the initial workflow trigger: a user submits a request via the DT APIs, which is passed to the DTO as an Orchestrator Task. The orchestrator validates the request, interprets the workflow definition, and initiates execution by dispatching the first tasks to the designated agents. In lines 4–7, the orchestrator issues commands to the agent proxies, which in turn interface with their agents. When an agent determines that additional data are needed, it signals this requirement by emitting a Data Task on the CB. The DH then processes this request, querying the appropriate external source or service. To ensure efficiency, results are cached in the Cache component, so that subsequent workflow steps can retrieve them without resending the query. Lines 8–10 represent the orchestration loop: once the requested data are available, the orchestrator resumes the suspended workflow step, forwarding the retrieved information to the waiting agent. The agent then completes its task and reports back through its proxy. As before, all intermediate results and context are managed externally, ensuring that both agents and orchestrator remain stateless and ready to handle further requests. Finally, in lines 11–12, the orchestrator assembles the workflow outputs and publishes the result.

Figure 34: Pipeline initiation and workflow management sequence.

Figure 35: Data and Agent Task execution sequence.

Conclusions

The work presented in this deliverable demonstrates how EU-DREAM builds on the foundations of REPLICA while introducing significant innovations to meet the project's requirements. Whereas REPLICA relied on distributed orchestration across its simulation and AI environments, EU-DREAM moves towards a centralised orchestration layer that brings global visibility, consistency, and scalability to pipeline execution. This shift addresses the limitations of distributed orchestration in complex workflows, where dependencies and interactions between multiple agents must be managed with precision.

A key design choice has been the adoption of a stateless orchestration model, supported by caching and asynchronous communication. This allows workflows to remain stateful in their execution logic while the orchestrator itself remains lightweight, replicable, and resilient to failure. Combined with a unified data model and the continued use of Kafka as the CB, this design ensures interoperability and efficiency while simplifying the integration of new agents.

The resulting architecture is therefore not just an adaptation of REPLICA, but an evolution: it retains proven elements such as modularity and event-driven communication, while adding centralised management, transparent APIs, and mechanisms for trust and reliability in data handling. These advances make EU-DREAM capable of supporting diverse scenarios, scaling to new use cases, and providing a robust foundation for DT applications in the energy domain.

In conclusion, EU-DREAM demonstrates how targeted enhancements to a proven architecture can unlock new levels of flexibility and performance. By centralising orchestration, enforcing stateless execution, and harmonising communication, the platform is well-positioned to deliver on its objectives of scalability, transparency, and reliability across distributed environments.

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